

WHY DO WE LOVE ONLINE SHOPPING: EXPLORING THE MINDS OF GENERATION Z

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Why Do We Love Online Shopping: Exploring the Minds of Generation Z

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Abstract

Online shopping for goods and services has become more common as a result of the Internet's remarkable expansion and growth over the past few decades. The number of people purchasing online has increased significantly, both in terms of quantity and global internet retail sales. This study utilized qualitative methods specifically multiple case study to investigate the reasons behind Generation Z's preference for internet shopping over conventional mall or market purchasing, characterize the challenges that they faced when making internet buying and the coping mechanism on how they address these difficulties. An interview is conducted with seven (7) grade 12 students. Various responses of participants were collected. Reasons, challenges and addressing difficulties by students were examined. The findings of this research revealed that practical benefits, comfort and accessibility, economic benefits, ease and efficiency are the reasons why generation Z loves online shopping rather than traditional purchasing. The students' challenges in purchasing online are operational challenges, trust and security concerns, and satisfaction and expectation gaps. Support and guidance, proactive management, and personal growth are keys to addressing the challenges. The findings indicate a new conception of why generation Z loves online shopping. In keeping with this, the recipients might think about lowering their expectations, protecting personal information, checking internet connection, accepting responsibility of choices, asking customers for advice, and learning from mistakes.

Keywords: *online shopping, Generation Z, preference, ABM, conventional shopping*

Introduction

As an online shopper, we have delightful experiences in purchasing online. It enhances the way, as customers, encounter and engage with the brand and products during our purchasing journey. Online shopping for goods and services has become more common as a result of the Internet's remarkable expansion and growth over the past few decades. Therefore, the internet has made possible a more expansive and fascinating market for the new consumer generation. Online shopping is any form of sale that is done over the internet. The development in online sales that has been observed can be attributed to the advantages of the Internet, which include the availability of a large amount of affordable and timely information. In addition, Kenyans have been using the internet a lot. As per a report published by the Kenyan Communication Authority, e-commerce in Kenya is valued at 4.3 billion. Billion as opposed to Sh54 billion in South Africa, whereas in Morocco and Egypt, it is roughly 9.6 billion and 17 billion, respectively (Kebandi & Reuben, 2019).

On the other hand, the number of people purchasing online has increased significantly, both in terms of quantity and global internet retail sales. In New Zealand, 52% of internet buyers returned an item or goods they had purchased online at least once in 2018, despite the lack of data regarding the percentage of returns. Furthermore, because delivery vehicles are frequently underutilized while meeting the expectations of online shoppers for greater levels of service (such as same-day or urgent delivery), the operational efficiency of courier businesses has been impacted. Because they are the ones who pay for the service, this places a lot of pressure on online merchants, making it difficult for them to stay profitable while maintaining their competitive advantage in the market (Media, 2020).

Moreover, the increasing number of organizations offering online services and businesses has led to the rise in popularity of e-commerce. It is through a transaction involving a business and a consumer. On the other hand, the tech titan Meta, who owns Facebook, has disclosed data regarding the online purchasing habits of Filipinos. According to the poll, even if Filipino consumers are visiting physical stores again, their online purchasing habits from the pandemic still matter. More so, online marketplace purchases were popular because of the worldwide lockdown, social isolation, and other measures to halt the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, pushing customers to make more purchases on e-commerce platforms. Therefore, the corporate climate changed quickly as a result of the quarantine (Gu et al., 2021; Taher, 2021; The Manila Times, 2022).

Additionally, the way that consumers shop is significantly increasing the internet retail sector's profitability. Typically, shopping habits of consumers are crucial because they help businesses better understand the elements that affect their customers. Online shoppers are more cost-effective and have easier access to information than those who purchase in physical locations. Consumer behaviour is the result of a person's behaviour and emotions when they go shopping. A variety of unique elements influence consumer behaviour, some of which the retailer may take advantage of. Consequently, to find out what works best in a specific store, it is essential to take consumer behaviour into account. From there, you can discover how to make the most of these features, boost sales, and enhance the customer experience (Kelwig, 2022; Nicoleta, 2022).

Here at Malalag Cogon National High School, online purchasing has taken on a life of its own. For as much as it is so convenient and offers a large selection of products, easy price comparison, 24/7 accessibility, and the comfort of home shopping, online shopping is quite beneficial. In addition to the trends, students were overly eager to shop online, particularly when friends or other people

recommended a product to them. As the researchers have seen, students at Malalag Cogon National High School engage in online sales as well. Typically, they make the investment to become sellers in order to meet their own needs. Based on the informal interviews we have conducted with some students, some of their responses about their considered preferences towards online shopping are very useful and time saving. They prefer online shopping due to products are less than the actual price by the cause of vouchers, giveaways, etc.

In addition, in a casual interview we have conducted, many students responded that they would rather shop online than visit the grocery store since it is convenient and easy to compare products, choose what to buy and compare it to other options, get accurate and relevant information about products or services, and, in the case of online sellers, a properly checked transaction will go through without any issues. Especially in this generation, where everything is done online, the researchers can also see that all of the students are more likely to add items to their carts or purchase the items they desire online. The only benefit of online shopping is that there are a lot of products to pick from, and it will be easy to locate what you are looking for.

Additionally, online buying has altered how customers purchase goods and services. Due to its simplicity of use, accessibility, and convenience, online shopping is growing in popularity. Understanding the components of the online shopping experience has become crucial as current conceptualizations of this architecture are still disorganized. There are various definitions of what an online purchase is, given the variety of consumer experience studies. Usability is the term used to describe how consumers view the advantages and appropriateness of online buying. Customers' ability to use and navigate an online shopping website or app is a key indicator of its usability. Enjoyment is linked to feelings of pleasure and happiness. Trust is a key element affecting how people see internet shopping. Online shoppers must feel secure knowing that their personal information is protected and that the websites they visit are safe. Trust influences a favorable attitude toward online purchase (Al-Khateeb et al., 2023).

The purpose of this study is to investigate the reasons behind Generation Z's preference for internet shopping over conventional mall or market purchasing. Therefore, the goal of this study is to analyze why Generation Z prefers online shopping rather than face-to-face contact. This study also aims to characterize the challenges that Generation Z faced when making internet purchases and the way they address these difficulties.

These are the theories in which this study will be anchored. First is the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) which describes how people behave in social situations when they are under the influence of certain factors, acting out of certain reasons, and doing so in a planned manner. The factors that influence the goal of behaviour include attitude towards behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behaviour control. Before a behaviour in humans can emerge, it must first be determined why it is being done. In addition, in order to explain people's behaviour in accordance with their own free will, the Theory of Planned Behaviour was established and is widely employed in scientific research. Behaviour determines behavioral intent, claims this idea, which is widely used to explain people's reactions to various circumstances. The subjectivity norm (the impact of family members) and the individual's attitude shape the behavioral intention (Erten, 2002; Koç & Turan, 2014).

Figure 1. *The Model of Theory of Planned Behavior*

Another theory that supports this study is the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Specifically, it is one of the most significant ideas in the Management Information Systems (MIS) literature, which was created to measure people's acceptance and adaptation of technology as well as to explain people's behaviour in general and their use or lack thereof. TAM is a general model that can help explain the variables influencing the adoption of technology, or in our example, the behaviour of online shoppers. The key elements that explain why technology is accepted are perceived utility and perceived simplicity of use. This model aims to predict and comprehend people's purpose, behaviour, and attitude towards using technology. They originate from the fields of psychology, information systems, and sociology. When evaluating the various aspects that impact the adoption of online buying, these models from information system research and behavioral psychology are compatible, since online purchasing is an act of behaviour that is dependent on the internet. Online shopping adoption can be studied with the help of theories of technology adoption, which explain the factors that influence people's decisions about adopting and using new technologies (Liao & Cheung, 2001; Mijoska, 2017).

The nature of online shopping and generating the minds of Generation Z can suggest multiple important Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), which are Goal 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth and Goal 12: Responsible Consumption and Production.

Figure 2. *The Model of Technology Acceptance Model*

Firstly, the Eighth Goal: Decent Work and Economic Growth. In addition to full and productive employment and decent labour for all, this goal seeks to achieve sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth. Additionally, it supports policies that are development-oriented and encourage innovation, entrepreneurship, and the creation of respectable jobs as well as productive activities. The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development aims to sustain per capital economic growth, particularly in least-developed countries, by achieving 7% growth per year. It also focuses on achieving higher levels of economic productivity through diversification, technological upgrading, and innovation. The agenda also promotes development-orientated policies that support productive activities, job creation, entrepreneurship, creativity, and innovation. It also aims to improve global resource efficiency and decouple economic growth from environmental degradation.

The Twelfth Goal, however, is Responsible Production and Consumption. With industrialized nations setting the example, the 10-year Framework of Programs on Sustainable Consumption and Production Patterns seeks to establish sustainable patterns of consumption and production throughout the world. The objective is to manage natural resources effectively, limit waste generation, handle chemicals and garbage responsibly, and cut down on per capital global food waste by 2030. Businesses must to embrace sustainable practices and incorporate sustainability data into their reporting schedules. Sustainable procurement methods should be used by the public sector, and individuals should be informed about sustainable lifestyles and development. Furthermore, in order to safeguard emerging nations and their populations, instruments for tracking the effects of sustainable development and rationalizing fossil fuel subsidies had to be created. Overall, this research can lead to the successful implementation of the SDG's and the accomplishment of their primary objectives. While the goal of the researchers is to publish related outputs that allow the community to learn about complex development challenges, generate renewed commitments to address them, and provide practical means for effective implementation to balance the community's economic, social, and environmental dimensions.

Additionally, the researchers feel a great sense of urgency in finishing this investigation. Understanding the variables influencing consumer behaviour and determining the connection between online buying habits and generation Z (customer) happiness with purchases are the goals of research on online shopping. Usually, it is done to boost or enhance the worth, calibre, and allure of benefits for customers and promote greater contentment. In order to better and modify the behaviour of the generation z as customers or online shoppers, this study will innovate in that regard. Therefore, the outcome of this study will be useful to the following beneficiaries:

Online Sellers: With the help of this study, vendors can learn more about how the changes in online shopping might affect their business, increase customer loyalty, and help customers buy their products in an informed manner. It might also provide them with insights into how to improve the value of their customers' delight, streamline their operations, and eventually boost income.

Online Shoppers/Purchasers: Through this study, they may enhance their purchasing experiences by making them more pleasurable and seamless. Improve customer service by gaining knowledge of frequently asked questions and preferences, which will assist in improving, resolving and handling issues more skilfully. They can also be informed when making decisions and how to address the encountered challenges. Customers can learn more about their own buying habits and preferences, which may help them make better-informed judgement about what to buy, making their experience safer and more effective.

Generation Z: They can gain insight into the inclinations and actions of their own generation through this study, which will aid various companies in creating marketing plans that will guarantee higher levels of involvement. Additionally, by analyzing the shopping patterns of their generation, which will provide hints about future consumer trends, they may improve their coping challenges and experiences utilizing various platforms.

Parents of the Shoppers: This is crucial to the buyer's parents in this study as well. Given that a large portion of Generation Z customers are still in their formative years, it is preferable for parents to share their tastes and insights with their children via internet shopping, allowing them to better guide their children in making judgement about what to buy.

Researchers: This study will contribute to the academic and practical understanding of researchers in the e-commerce by providing valuable data on consumer behaviour, preferences, and trends. As a result, it enriches the body of knowledge and offers practical insights that can advance industry practices and academic research.

Literature Review

In the twenty-first century, with most people leading busy lives and stressful schedules, online purchasing has become increasingly vital. Online purchasing turned out to be the most practical and convenient option for them in this circumstance. Online shopping has transformed consumer behavior and expanded quickly to a worldwide scale. A type of e-commerce known as "online shopping" enables

customers to use the Internet to directly buy products or services from sellers. Other names for this type of store are online store, virtual store, Internet shop, web-store, and e-shop. Online stores create a physical experience that is similar to purchasing goods and services from an online retailer; this type of online shopping is known as business-to-consumer online shopping. Online shopping is the process by which customers choose to purchase goods via the internet (Singh & Sailo, 2013).

Using electronic marketing and online communication, businesses plan a range of marketing activities, such as market research, product development, advertising, customer support, customer feedback, and educating consumers about the features of products. Online shopping is used as a communication and electronic commerce medium to boost or improve the value, quality, and appeal of offering consumer benefits and increased satisfaction. There are benefits and drawbacks to shopping online. Internet consumers are generally discouraged from making purchases online due to credit card theft, privacy issues, non-delivery risk, and uncertainty about the quality of goods and services. Making purchases online is referred to as "online buying behavior" in this context. For instance, when a consumer knows they must purchase a book, they shop online, acquiring information along the way and weighing all of their options before selecting the one that best meets their needs (Sultan & Uddin 2011).

The abundance of offers that internet shops have started to provide has significantly increased online traffic. Online purchasing might seem unsafe and unreliable to some customers, even with all of its benefits. The study suggested that loyalty and trust are strongly correlated, with consumers typically having significantly greater faith in brands than in the stores that carry them. Because there is no in-person interaction between the merchant and the customer when purchasing online, it is not socializing and the customer may find it difficult to build trust. For a potential consumer to become an actual customer, they must have faith in the online business. Due to its convenience and comfort, online shopping is becoming more and more popular. When making a purchase online, a customer could have both good and bad experiences. Despite the many advantages, some consumers still do not like internet shopping as their primary method of purchasing, according to some previous research (Daroch et al., 2021).

There are numerous justifications for internet shopping. Customers, for instance, can purchase anything whenever they want to minimize pressure when interacting face-to-face with salespeople; they can locate the same thing at a lesser price by comparing other websites at the same time; they can avoid traffic jams in stores, etc. These elements can be categorized into four groups: information, products and services that are available, cost and time efficiency, and convenience. Customers might obtain the identical thing they would buy in-store at a reduced cost when they shop online because they are frequently presented with better deals. Given that internet retailers provide a wide range of goods and services to their clientele. Compared to purchasing from neighborhood retail establishments, users have greater opportunities to compare prices across multiple websites and locate products at reduced costs (Katawetawaraks & Wang, 2011).

Methodology

Research Design

Understanding the phenomena in context-specific settings—such as a "real world setting, where the researcher does not attempt to manipulate the phenomenon of interest"—is the goal of qualitative research (Patton, 2002).

In this study, the type of Qualitative Research Design to be used is the Multiple Case Study. It is a tried and tested approach for getting a thorough grasp of a given phenomenon, such the information-seeking habits of a certain user base. Many studies conducted over the past 20 years have shown that, despite the case study method's opponent who doubt its rigor, it can be an effective tool for delving deeper into a situation and offering a rich context for comprehending the phenomenon being studied (Zach, 2006).

Moreover, a particular tradition within the qualitative research paradigm is represented by the case study. It seeks to generate more general theoretical claims regarding regularities in the observable events while simultaneously striving to arrive at a thorough comprehension of the event under study. Compared to other, more analytical methods, case studies can provide a much fuller and more vivid picture of the phenomenon under study since they are designed to immerse the reader in the world of the subject or subjects. Furthermore, case studies are typically utilized, along with other traditions under the qualitative research paradigm, when researchers want to gain a thorough understanding of a very limited number of people, issues, or circumstances (Creswell, 1998; Fidel, 1984; Marshall & Rossman, 2014; Patton, 1990).

The conflict between generality, accuracy, and simplicity—by which he meant both the study's simplicity and the conclusions' understandability—was succinctly described in a piece about writing about research in organizations. Generality comes at the expense of accuracy; while a large-scale study (like a widely dispersed survey) may yield results that can be broadly applied to a variety of organizations, it is unlikely that the results will provide an accurate depiction of any one organization. However, case study research also experiences this conflict since "confident generalizations" are sacrificed in order to gain a deeper grasp of the phenomenon being studied. It is regarding how well the findings apply to people, issues, or circumstances that fall outside the purview of the research (Patton, 1990; Weick, 1979).

In addition, a case study is defined as "an investigation into a bounded system." a scheme, occurrence, undertaking, or people. Moreover through the use of a replication technique, the multiple-case studies design enables the researcher to investigate the phenomenon being studied. The replication strategy's application is evaluated against carrying out several independent trials on related subjects. There are

two steps to replication: a literal stage when instances are chosen to produce comparable outcomes as much as possible, and a theoretical replication step, where instances are chosen to investigate and validate or refute the patterns found in the original cases. There are no strict guidelines on how many instances must be included in the multiple-case studies design in order to meet the replication strategy's requirements. According to the author, if the outcomes match the predictions, six to ten cases should be enough to "provide compelling support for the initial set of propositions". In the multiple-case studies technique, "the typical criteria regarding sample size are irrelevant" because it does not rely on the kind of representative sampling logic associated with survey research. Therefore, the number of instances needed to reach saturation, or to continue collecting data until no meaningful new discoveries are found, is how sample size is instead calculated. The sample members ought to be specifically chosen to include situations when the phenomena being studied is probably going to occur (Creswell, 1998; Yin, 1994).

Participants

Participants in this study were Grade 12 online buyers with prior experienced making purchases online. Participants in this study were the purposely chosen seven (7) Grade 12 learners. They were chosen because the researchers are interested in learning more about their behavior as customers when purchasing online, that helped them look into their experiences that are different and became the same.

The researchers prepared inclusion and exclusion in determining the participants. For the inclusion criterion, participants need to be online consumers who use applications to shop online, make purchases online, and deal with a variety of issues related to online shopping. They should be students who are currently enrolled in MCNHS in the current school year. The study will not include participants who do not use online apps for purchasing or who are not online consumers. Thus, only individuals who meet the qualifications are the subject of this study.

Instrument

The researcher employed an open-ended interview guide during the in-depth interviews. The guides consisted of questions, themes, or a combination of both, ranging from structured to unstructured. By being accommodating, the interviewer(s) enabled participants to elaborate on their initial responses, yielding richer data for the research project (Smulowitz, 2017).

The interview guide questionnaires helped with the interview guide creation in several ways. An interview guide was a brief synopsis of the key points to be discussed during the interview and the key questions the researcher wanted the participants to answer for each point. The researchers typically confined the guide to one page to make it easy to refer to and avoid getting too detailed. Creating such a guide helped focus and organize the questions and study path of the researcher. One method involved interviewing the subject, which comprised using a structured or semi-structured guide to ask specific questions to gain a deeper understanding of their viewpoints (Aung, Razak, & Nazry, 2021).

Procedure

One of the most crucial phases of conducting research is gathering data. Gathering and measuring information on variables of interest in a systematic and defined manner allows one to test hypotheses, analyze results, and respond to research questions. This process is known as data collecting. On the other hand, the majority of qualitative data are not numerical and are either nominal or descriptive in nature. This indicates that words and phrases make up the data that has been gathered. Open-ended inquiries are used in qualitative research. Focus groups, group discussions, and interviews are examples of qualitative approaches. To learn more about the impacts and unexpected repercussions of a program, qualitative methods are useful (Mazhar, Anjum, Anwar & Khan, 2021). Below are the procedures in gathering the data:

Creating interview guide. It is necessary for the researchers to create guiding questions that the subject professor will validate. In order for the participants to complete the questionnaire fully aware of their responsibilities as the study's subjects, the researchers must explain a few terms to them.

Acquire authorization and access. Permissions must be accessed by the researchers. It is through obtaining authorization to access data sources and the case setting. The researchers also need to be aware of the ethical considerations. It is by guaranteeing the implementation of moral principles like informed consent to the participants and data privacy.

Gather information. To obtain detailed information, the researchers will conduct surveys and interviews with the subjects in this step. They must ask open-ended questions. The next step is document analysis, which includes reviewing and extracting pertinent data from case-related documents.

Arrange and Examine Data. Researchers will perform data management by methodically arranging the information they have gathered. This could entail classifying papers, analyzing observation notes, and transcribing interviews. However, this also falls under the category of data analysis where themes, patterns, and insights are found through the application of qualitative research methodologies. This may entail categorizing answers, searching for recurrent themes, and synthesizing results. Thus, after analyzing the data, the recorded audio of answers of the respondents will be deleted.

Interpreting Findings. The researcher will synthesize data in this section. They will combine knowledge from many data sources to provide a thorough grasp of the situation. Contextualize Results are another requirement that they must meet. It is to: Consider how the

case study adds to the knowledge of the research subject; relate findings to a wider context or body of literature.

Ethical Considerations

When performing qualitative research, ethical factors must be taken into account, as this study clarifies. Researcher duties to their participants, audience, society, and academic communities are at the heart of ethics. To make sure that they have followed the rules of ethical research, researchers can consult a few ethical guidelines. This essay outlines the general ethical principles that should be upheld when gathering and processing data for qualitative research. Conflict of interest and respect ethics, relationships with participants, informed permission, confidentiality, anonymity, reporting back to participants, the reliability of research, and translation concerns are a few of these (Mirza, Mirza & Bellalem, 2023).

The concept of privacy is both morally and legally sound. The legal notion pertains to the legal protection that an individual has been granted to regulate the use and access of personal data. Confidentiality and security are implemented within the general framework that privacy provides. Different jurisdictions have different privacy protections, which are outlined in laws and regulations. The right of individuals to have their data protected during storage, transport, and usage in order to stop unauthorized disclosure is known as confidentiality. The proper use and sharing of health information should be covered in confidentiality policies and procedures, together with a methodical analysis of moral and legal concerns as outlined in privacy laws and regulations (UNAIDS/PEPFAR, 2016).

In order to demonstrate that the research participant or respondent has chosen to participate in the study of their own free will, researchers must always provide an Informed Consent Form (ICF) with every proposal involving human subjects. The mother tongue of the potential participants should be used to write the forms; if this is not English, an English translation should be included. Written in the language the researcher feels most comfortable with, consent forms can be translated into the participants' home tongue and English. To ensure accuracy, translated consent forms should ideally be back-translated and compared to the original. Both the English and local language versions of the ICF should be submitted for evaluation (World Health Organization, 2013).

One of the almost universal features of social interactions in the real world is voluntary participation: in many naturally occurring settings, people have the freedom to choose whether or not to collaborate with others. Real-world examples of organizations dealing with collective action issues include voluntary associations, collectives, community groups, and collaborative institutions. In these organizations, agents are free to participate in the shared activities or choose not to. In fact, voluntary participation is occasionally used to justify why these groups are rather successful at resolving problems involving collective action. However, little is known about the mechanisms underpinning the widely held belief that voluntary engagement may promote collaboration (Nosenzo & Tufano, 2017).

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data, discussions, and results of the findings of the study. Just as the manner in which the data were gathered, the findings were arranged into three tables, which include the reasons why generation Z loves online shopping, the challenges that they encountered while purchasing online, and the way they cope up with these difficulty.

Profile of Participants

Table 1. Profile of Participants

Participant Code Name	Age	Grade Level	Used App
P1L1	17	Grade 12	Shopee
P2L2	17	Grade 12	Shopee
P3L3	18	Grade 12	Tiktok Shop
P4L4	17	Grade 12	Tiktok Shop
P5L5	18	Grade 12	Shopee
P6L6	17	Grade 12	Tiktok Shop
P7L7	18	Grade 12	Shopee

The study found four (4) major themes in the participants' reasons for using online shopping. Namely: practical benefits, comfort and accessibility, economic benefits, and ease and efficiency.

Table 2. Reasons For Using Online Shopping

Core Ideas	Major Theme
It gives a lesser hassle. It saves more time. Much more convenient. Advantage of faster purchasing.	Practical Benefits
Good outcome despite of it's low-priced (cost-effective). No need to go out. It is easy to access.	Comfort and accessibility
A lot of cheaper items/products and affordable. Available discounts and sales	Economic Benefits
It does not take a lot of energy to struggle yourself.	Ease and Efficiency

More easier to buy.

Less tiring; more helpful.

Practical Benefits

The first major theme that emerge from the participants' justifications for using internet shopping is the practical benefits of it. Customers that purchase online reported that they always adhere to the advantages that come with doing so. The students who made the purchases mentioned that using and shopping online offers several advantages. These useful, applicable, and factual features contribute to any beneficial outcome and are one of the primary motivations of their generation's love of online shopping.

The result is supported by the study on the Consumer Attitudes Towards Online Grocery Shopping which revealed that customers cited time savings, variety in a single store, and ease of ordering as the main benefits of online shopping. Phone calls and web pages were thought to be less convenient than mobile applications. The majority of respondents (89%) had positive opinions on grocery shopping online, while the remaining respondents had negative opinions. The results also show that 52% of those surveyed knew about web portals. When grocery buying online, freshness and delivery time were prioritized over payment methods and cost (Saban & Arun, 2016).

The main theme's primary concepts are the benefits that users experience when they shop online. Online customers emphasize that it is a hassle-free transaction and that they do not have to go to busy venues. Additionally, the statements of the participants generate the belief that online purchasing is convenient and time-saving. They have stated that since online shopping is quicker, they don't have to waste time traveling to malls or other conventional locations to make purchases. In fact, the participant shared that:

"I use online apps as to online shopping because it was much more accessible to this days like technology based or 21st century use a lot of gadgets to navigate in daily lives, so hindi siya hassle pag pupunta ng mall, like that. Because your only in your house to just add to cart, ship it and perceive this item". P2L2

("I use online apps as to online shopping because it was much more accessible to this days like technology based or 21st century use a lot of gadgets to navigate in daily lives, so it is not hassle to go to the mall, like that. Because your only in your house to just add to cart, ship it and perceive this item".)

Comfort and Accessibility

Accessibility and comfort are the second key factor that comes up when talking about why Generation Z prefers online shopping. According to the participants, it is not exhausting and is accessible anywhere. where everyone can access it without restriction. Customers are free to select or buy the things that are best for them. They are therefore more likely to shop online as a result.

Online Shopping: An Overview supports the study's findings by demonstrating that consumers may browse online retailers from the comfort of their homes and make purchases while seated in front of a computer. Many customers have internet access at home and at work, and online retailers are typically open twenty-four hours a day. Therefore, they find online shopping to be very convenient. The fact that internet shopping eliminates the need to wait in line or browse a store for a specific item is one of its most alluring features, especially during the holiday season. A wide range of products are offered online (Sunitha & Gnanadhas, 2014).

The cost-effectiveness of purchasing, reduced disruption, and the ease of obtaining certain things through internet shopping are the elements they aimed to highlight. They also mention that it is more comfortable to use because all they need to do is click with their devices at any time or any location. They claimed that going out might be exhausting and expensive. Actually, according to the participant:

"Kay kung sa mall magpalit mas layo kung mag online lang man mas mapadali sya mas less pajud ug time tas sa balay raka ninyo okay lang dali ra maglingkod lang ka". P6L6

("Because if you buy at the mall, it's further away, if you buy online, it's easier, less time, it's okay , it's easy, just sit down.")

Economic Benefits

The economic benefits come in third. The participants indicated that they favored online purchasing due to its many benefits, including financial ones. Many people become excited when they discover the advantages of internet shopping that aren't always available or practiced in traditional retail. They find that shopping online saves a lot of money. These factors also give them the confidence to use online apps more.

The result of the study is supported by Motivator of online shopping: The income factor revealed that with the exception of necessities and urgent products, shoppers are motivated by offers for all items. Even without any sales or discounts, the essential commodities would still be in demand. Discounts and promotions for other products affect consumers' purchasing decisions. A greater offer will result in a better sale. Additionally, in order to obtain a competitive edge, internet marketers must offer clients more valuable brands and products. All product categories nationwide should offer the cash on delivery option so that all customers can take advantage of it. Reverse logistics management requires careful consideration since, in the event that the consumer is dissatisfied with the product, there

should be a provision for them to pick it up from the supplied place (Mishra, 2015).

The main points of the economic advantages mentioned by the participants are that they prefer shopping online since there are many more affordable goods available, in addition to the fact that buying online is also very cost-effective. Another explanation is that they prefer internet shopping due to the numerous offers and discounts available for various products. Indeed, according to the participant:

“I love more shopping online kay if ever i have some product that I was interested there's always discount or sale which you can't yet get in legal stores or like mall stores because those products were already been entitled about their price because of their salary or something na maka apekto ng kanilang sales if ever na naa silay discount and it's much more necessary to buy products online because you don't know if its real like surprise it's a scam like that pero it's much more about the sale that's why we love online shopping”. P2L2

(“I love more shopping online because if ever i have some product that I was interested there's always discount or sale which you can't yet get in legal stores or like mall stores because those products were already been entitled about their price because of their salary or something that can affect their sales if ever they have a discount and it's much more necessary to buy products online because you don't know if its real like surprise, it's a scam like that, but it's much more about the sale that's why we love online shopping”.)

Ease and Efficiency

Finally, another factor contributing to Generation Z's love of internet buying is its convenience and effectiveness. According to the students we spoke with, they truly like shopping online because it can benefit them. The participants said that several of the items they purchased online were very helpful. Consumers who made their purchases online stated that they do anticipate the benefits of doing so. They adhered to the effectiveness of online shopping due to its ease of use.

A study on E-wom, Trust, Usefulness, Ease of use, and Online Shopping Via Websites: The Moderating Role Of Online Shopping Experience supports the findings, revealing that trust is a social component and ease of use is regarded as a technology embedded feature. The study's conclusions indicated a relationship between trust and simplicity of usage. Students' attitudes regarding using mobile social software and their faith in it are clear indicators of the relationships between them. Usefulness was the third factor examined. The study's results indicated that the perceived usefulness variable had a significant value of 0.01 and a coefficient of -0.09, both of which were greater than the alpha value of $\alpha = 0.05$. It is hypothesized that perceived usefulness has no effect on users' trust in the Opensooq website, indicating that perceived usefulness has no effect on users' behavior on the website because many customers do not use online features to buy or sell. Nonetheless, it can be said that the study's results do not bear any resemblance to those of earlier studies by Amin, Rezaei, and Abolghasemi (2014); that implied utility is having a favorable relationship with the fourth and crucial element that was examined is trust. It is said to be the most crucial factor in predicting how customers would behave when they shop online (Chinomona, 2013; Bilal, Abdallah, Abdelbaset, Hassan & Odai, 2020).

According to the participants, the main idea of economic benefits is that it doesn't take much effort for them to enter a regular mall. Online shopping is more easy and they don't have to exert themselves to venture outside of their comfort zone. To put it another way, generation Z finds that internet apps are more useful while making purchases. The participant actually said that:

“The benefits that has given that I don't literally use my strength or energy to go to a local shops like mag commute, mag baklay ana and it's much more easier to buy and the benefits i get is about my health that I don't exhaust myself too much just to buy a product. It doesn't need a lot of energy to struggle yourself or hassle yourself just to buy a product that you want”. P2L2

(“The benefits that has given that I don't literally use my strength or energy to go to a local shops like commuting, walking, and it's much more easier to buy and the benefits i get is about my health, that I don't exhaust myself too much just to buy a product. It doesn't need a lot of energy to struggle yourself or hassle yourself just to buy a product that you want”.)

The study found three (3) major themes of challenges that the participants have encountered while purchasing online. These are: operational challenges, trust and security concerns, satisfaction and expectation gaps.

Table 3. *Challenges Encountered Using Online Shopping*

<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Major Theme</i>
Sometimes it is slow in internet.	Operational challenges
There are a lot of scams and fake products.	Trust and Security Concerns
Disappointments with the product.	Satisfaction and Expectation Gaps
The matter of expectations versus reality.	

Operational Challenges

Operational difficulties are the first significant subject among the difficulties faced by online shoppers. Online buyers are burdened by these difficulties when making purchases. The participants mentioned several challenges, which occasionally irritates them when they shop online. Due to unequal access, this has an impact on the fiercely competitive online environment.

The result of the study is supported by A Study on Opportunities and Challenges of Online Shopping in India revealed that with the

use of the internet, we can now access almost the entire world at our fingertips. The Internet has completely changed the retail landscape, and the rules of the game are rapidly evolving. Our society as a whole has been impacted by western culture. Not just in metropolitan areas but also in regular cities, life is getting faster. The number of nuclear families is rising, and since both spouses work, they have less time to occasionally visit the market to make purchases. Other arguments include time constraints, traffic, late work hours, the convenience of card money, and, most importantly, the availability of the internet to everyone who wants it. Gender and normative ideas moderate the behavior of online shoppers. Different age groups and the "ease of use" feature of a website influence consumers' attitudes regarding online purchasing. According to the research, online retailers can enhance how customers view a website's "convenience" feature (Raja, Sudha, Sathyanarayanan & Harikrishnan, 2021).

The slow internet in the Philippines is the main theme's central notion. Online consumers claim that when the internet is extremely slow, it can be quite difficult. The app logging may cause them to click on the incorrect button. They are defrauded as a result of this burden, and their poor internet prevents them from canceling. The participant has really stated that:

"Internet and also scams like that because when you have a slow internet you possibly like click the buy now button and you just lags and then it ships immediately in your exact duration within seven days that you don't know what would happen because of your slow internet that your app or online shop just that about it..." P2L2

Trust and Security Concerns

The challenges that online shoppers encounter are the second main subject. Concerns about security and trust are crucial for internet shoppers. Online shoppers are finding it difficult to make purchases due to the aforementioned difficulties. It is undeniable that certain products fall short of our expectations due to unforeseen circumstances. Additionally, it might not be sufficiently secured for you to have confidence in the seller.

The result of the study is supported by the Safety of Online Shopping According to Customers. System Safety: Human - Technical Facility - Environment revealed that Consumers are increasingly choosing to use the Internet to access a variety of services. They frequently make a variety of purchases. Regretfully, consumers report that there are issues with internet shopping. Consumers worry that the items they ordered won't arrive, won't live up to their expectations, or will break down in transit. The mode of payment for this kind of purchasing is equally crucial. In order to prevent financial loss in the event that the purchased products are not delivered, customers frequently choose to pay more for the option of payment on delivery (Ingaldi & Brozova, 2020).

The fundamental reason behind why trust and security issues are among the difficulties faced by online consumers is that, according to the customers, there are many scams and fake goods that make them uncomfortable. Purchasing online raises concerns about whether or not they trust it, according to their replies. The customer's decision is therefore very different. Actually, according to the participant:

"...The scams is entirely the most common struggle or issues that you will face when buying some products online because you don't know that's real and you don't know what's behind it so sometimes the products is a bit too off about your expectations". P2L2

Satisfaction and Expectation Gaps

The satisfaction and expectation gaps are the third aspect that contributes to the difficulties faced by online customers. According to the participants, the difference between expectations and reality about the purchased product is crucial. The participants also expressed their disappointment when certain things they had purchased fail to live up to their expectations. And it can have a detrimental effect on them. Furthermore, the reasons behind these difficulties do influence consumers' decisions to buy a product.

The result of the study supported by Customer Satisfaction in Online Shopping: a study into the reasons for motivations and inhibitions revealed that numerous factors influenced the purchases made by consumers. Customers are motivated to buy things online by all of these factors. Consumers believe that the greatest significant incentive for internet buying is "time saving." Other driving aspects for online shopping include "information availability," "open 24/7," "a wide variety of products/brands," "reasonable prices," "various offers for online products," "easy ordering system," and "shopping fun." Conversely, when asked about the barriers to online shopping, the respondents' top concerns were "online payment systems," "personal privacy or security issues," "delaying of delivery," "products mixing up at delivery time," and "products return policies," as well as "lack of personal customer service." Additionally, it was noted that some customers do not trust or rely on internet buying because of the online payment system and personal privacy alone (Karim, 2013).

Disappointments with the product and the issue of anticipation vs actuality are the key concepts of satisfaction and expectation gaps. The participants' responses indicate that the results greatly exceed their expectations. Their disappointments are very important. Because they were disappointed rather than pleased after reading the product reviews, they believed the quality was good. The participant actually said that:

"Disappointed sa mga products maabot saimoha nga dili mao maabot sya pero imong expectation kay katong naa sa picture". P3L3

("Disappointed with the products that arrived to me that did not arrive correctly, but what you expect is what is in the picture.")

The study found three (3) major themes of coping mechanisms in the challenges that the participants have encountered. These are:

support and guidance, proactive management and personal growth.

Table 4. *Coping Mechanisms in the Challenges Encountered*

<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Major Theme</i>
Seeking advices from the elders.	Support and Guidance
Navigate it properly to avoid some struggles.	Proactive Management
Address it properly to avoid scams and issues.	
Accept what comes and learn from mistakes and advices.	Personal Growth

Support and Guidance

The first main issue, support and guidance, addresses the difficulties that customers had when making purchases online. Customers say that assistance and guidance may have something to do with their desire to make purchases online. These strategies enable people to guarantee the security of the goods they have acquired. In light of this new concept, consumers can now make choices with the assistance and direction of those with greater experience.

The result of the study supported by A framework of online shopping support for information recommendations revealed that when making purchasing decisions, consumers lack adequate support. In other words, in order to help ISS find information to support shoppers, it is necessary to learn how shoppers search when they purchase online. "We assert that consumers' shopping-oriented queries are influenced by the e-marketing tactics used by sellers to market or sell their goods online (Lin, Cassaigne & Huan, 2010).

Asking elders for advice was one of the primary concepts of support and guidance that participants identified. Because they have greater expertise, customers appreciate the advice of elders while making internet purchases. These tips might help individuals use internet stores properly. Additionally, it may influence their choices when making online purchases. Participants say that product reviews assist them understand the specifics of the product they will receive. Consumers may peruse evaluations left by previous customers who have informed the seller that the product has fulfilled their expectations. They used online shopping more frequently after receiving support and direction. These new concepts changed their mindset and made them feel more at ease when making purchases from online retailers. The participant actually said that:

"Seeking some advice with my sisters my parents so i can address it properly..." P2L2

Proactive Management

The second main theme that consumers employed to deal with the difficulties that arise while making purchases online is proactive management. According to customers, proactive management enables them to plan for recognized hazards. Customers may experience a variety of effects from proactive management. Without it, they might not be able to account for the dangers that come with making purchases online. They benefit from this as well because it makes their order more successful.

The result of the study supported by the communication strategies of shopping centers in proactive and reactive crisis communication, revealed that effective crisis communication techniques can help entities overcome crises that could endanger their existence and have a negative impact on their future. While reactive crisis communication is defined as research on influencing crisis perception, reviving the image, or improving the image, pre-crisis proactive crisis communication is defined as anticipating the aspects of a crisis and taking proactive measures related to them. Consequently, the current pertinent practices as well as places for improvement will be identified (Kuşay, 2017).

The key to overcoming the difficulties of online shopping is being able to effectively browse everything in order to prevent problems and deal with them. Consumers have stated that before adding a product to their cart, they must definitely check for reviews. It's also because buyers need to be sure they're getting what they requested. Participants also mentioned that if you are aware of all the possible outcomes during the purchasing process, everything will go as planned. Finally, this influences consumers to be less restrained. The participant actually said that:

"...I know how to navigate it properly to avoid some struggles and to avoid scams like or to avoid issues so by that advices i address it easily so i can investigate more about the products more about the shops before buying some items." P2L2

Personal Growth

Finally, personal growth plays a role in helping customers cope with the challenges of online shopping. Participants acknowledge that they make mistakes. They further explain that customers can learn from these errors and use that knowledge to make better decisions in the future. Personal development could have a favorable impact on customers. It's possible that they won't use the same lessons learned from their failures the next time.

The result of the study supported by the An analysis of the impact of personality traits towards augmented reality in online shopping revealed that when it comes to online shopping, augmented reality greatly increases the buying intention.

The findings also show correlations between personality traits and online purchasing behaviors, such as neuroticism and openness to new experiences, which are linked to an increased propensity to make purchases online. Conversely, it has been demonstrated that

personality factors can predict impulsive purchasing, with low emotional stability and a high external locus of control carrying the largest weight (Lixândriou, Cazan & Maican, 2021).

The main concept that guarantees that consumers will encounter difficulties while making purchases online is acknowledging that they may encounter any obstacle, learn from their mistakes, and implement the stated recommendations. These elements will enable customers to attain greater success in life.

Additionally, participants acknowledged that while we all make mistakes, we must learn from them and use them to improve future events. Indeed, the participant stated that:

“Sa akoa kay naa man gud ta sa mindanao so lisod jud ipabalik ang parcel ginadawat nng jud nako nya next time dapat ako najud tan awon ang mga reviews dapat tan awon jud nako kung legit ba or nindot jud ang quality sa product nga mapalit nako.” P4L4

(“In my case, we are in Mindanao, so it is difficult to return the parcel. I will accept it but next time I will check if the product I can buy is legit or good quality.”)

Cross Case Analysis

Case #1: The case of Ms. Shopee

Ms. Shopee loves internet shopping because it's convenient, she can shop from home, she doesn't have to go out, and it's easy to get things. The difficulty she had was putting her trust in internet retailers. She overcomes this difficulty by managing expectations, being adaptive and flexible, accepting what happens, concentrating on the here and now, and embracing flaws.

Case #2: The case of Mr. Lazada

Mr. Lazada enjoys buying online because it's convenient, accessible, and eliminates the need to visit malls in person. It has reduced prices, sales, and discounts. Very comfortable, energy-efficient, and time-saving. Slow internet connectivity, lagging or delayed responses, unexpected orders brought on by technical difficulties, fraud and scams, product expectations, quality, and unfulfilled expectations are some of the difficulties he faced. He tackles these difficulties by asking family members for assistance, looking for help navigating internet shopping, researching products and stores, doing research before making purchases, and taking preventative action to stay clear of problems and frauds.

Case #3: The case of Ms. Tiktok Shop

The benefits of online shopping, according to Ms. Tiktok purchase, include lower energy costs, a wider selection of products, the ability to purchase during busy times, and the ability to avoid crowded malls and stores. Product mismatch, misleading advertising/inaccurate product representations, unfulfilled expectations, difficulty returning or exchanging things, unclear product information, and inadequate customer service are the difficulties she faced. She resolves these issues by working with delivery providers, communicating with the vendor successfully, voicing complaints clearly, initiating returns or exchanges, and requesting reimbursements.

Case #4: The case of Mr. Temu

Easy access and a quicker shopping experience are the main reasons Mr. Temu enjoys shopping online. It is quite reasonably priced and offers promotions and discounts. has the capacity to save time and shop from any location at any time. Among the difficulties he faced were low-quality goods at reasonable costs, overstated or inaccurate product promises, fraud and scams, and unrealistic expectations. In order to overcome these obstacles, he must accept the circumstances, learn from them, read product reviews, confirm the validity of the product, and assess its quality.

Case #5: The case of Mr. Walmart

Mr. Walmart enjoys buying online because it saves time, is easy to use, avoids physical exertion, and is accessible. Scams and fraud, counterfeit goods, misrepresentation and misinformation, and the difference between predicted and real product quality among the difficulties he faced. In order to overcome these obstacles, he manages expectations and is adaptive and flexible.

Case #6: The case of Mr. Amazon

Mr. Amazon like buying online because it's practical, hassle-free, easier, takes less time, and allows him to relax at home. Fortunately, he had no trouble making the online purchase. However, he will deal with it by accepting mistakes as unavoidable and embracing imperfection.

Case #7: The case of Ms. Shein

Ms. Shein loves buying online since it's easier, less expensive, cheaper, and requires less shipping than going to a physical store. It also saves money on transportation. She faced several difficulties, including lost money, wasted time and energy, dissatisfaction with customer support, and a lack of confidence in internet vendors. In order to overcome these obstacles, she adopts a "make-do" mentality, prioritizes practicality above perfection, accepts what comes, is self-aware, and manages expectations.

Conclusions

The researchers thoroughly examined the Generation Z's preference for online shopping which is driven by a combination of practical benefits, comfort and accessibility, economic benefits, and ease and efficiency. The first benefit of internet buying is that it saves clients time and bother by eliminating the need to visit physical stores. The ability to purchase whenever and anywhere you want follows, which makes online shopping more convenient and accessible. Third, online shopping is more appealing to Generation Z because it offers a wide range of reasonably priced products, discounts, and special offers. Finally, it is more convenient because it enables quick and simple transactions, which fits with Generation Z's desire for little effort and maximum results when making purchases. As a result, Generation Z loves to shop online mainly due to the deals and advantages that suit their needs.

When Generation Z made their first online purchase, they faced a number of serious difficulties that negatively affected their experience. These include gaps in satisfaction and expectations, operational challenges, and trust and security concerns. Slow internet connections and technological issues like app crashes or delays that cause them to become frustrated and make mistakes in transactions are some of the problems that Generation Z faces. Associated problems with online security transactions, fraud, phony goods, and deceptive tactics. Another concerns the expectations that customers have of the goods, which might cause them to be disappointed and dissatisfied. Online purchasing may therefore have many advantages, but it also has drawbacks.

Although it can be tough to shop online, consumers have created useful coping mechanisms to get through the challenges. Among these tactics are support and guidance, which involves reading product evaluations and asking knowledgeable people for help. Proactive management involves anticipating possible risks and acting quickly to avoid problems and guarantee successful transactions. Finally, embracing failures as teaching moments, adjusting to new circumstances, and applying lessons learned to enhance subsequent online buying experiences are all examples of personal growth. Generation Z improves their online buying experiences by implementing these tactics.

Following a thorough analysis, the researchers offer some suggestions. When it comes to the product that will be delivered to them, Generation Z should lower their expectations. Online buyers have to be careful with their personal information to prevent fraud and scams. In order to monitor the product's proper delivery, the sellers should also maintain communication with the buyers. Customers should exercise patience if it takes a while for their package to arrive. To prevent lags, customers ought to verify their internet connection before making a purchase on the internet.

To prevent dissatisfaction they must take responsibility for their product selections. To determine whether the goods is of good quality, customers should inspect the store. Generation Z should ask their elders, who have a great deal of experience with internet shopping, for suggestions. They have to appropriately handle it to prevent problems and scams. Additionally, people have to learn from their mistakes and accept what comes about. By following these suggestions, the beneficiaries will be able to make a better online shopping experience.

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